

From Households to GDP: Financial Literacy and Household Investment Behavior in India's \$5 Trillion Growth Mission (World Third largest economy in 2030)

Prof. Shubham B. Khemnar¹, Mr. Anuj S. Jagtap² & Mr. Ramchandra S. Kadam³

Department of Statistics,

New Arts Commerce and Science Collage, Ahilyanagar

Corresponding Author – Prof. Shubham B. Khemnar

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Abstract:

India aims to become the world's third-largest economy with a GDP target of about 5 trillion US dollars. Along with policy reforms and industrial growth, household financial behavior plays an important role because household consumption forms a major share of India's GDP. Decisions about saving, spending, borrowing, and investing at the family level directly affect national economic growth.

This study uses data from the NSS 77th Round – All India Debt and Investment Survey (2019), conducted by the National Sample Survey Office, to examine how financial literacy and spending habits influence capital formation. The research follows three stages: building a 2019 financial baseline, comparing with recent trends, and projecting outcomes up to 2030.

Statistical methods used include descriptive statistics, Gini coefficient and Lorenz curve, chi-square tests, logistic regression, K-Means clustering, PCA, and LDA. The results show how asset allocation, debt patterns, and financial inclusion affect productive investment and long-term growth. The study suggests that improving financial literacy and expanding formal financial access can help households contribute more effectively to India's economic growth goals.

Keywords: *GDP, Household Consumption, Financial Literacy, Financial Assets, Debt, Productive Investment, Economic Growth, etc.*

Introduction:

India aims to become the world's third-largest economy and reach a GDP of around 5 trillion US dollars in the coming years. Achieving this target requires not only strong industries and government policies, but also sound financial behavior at the household level. In India, household consumption contributes a major share of GDP. Therefore, the way families save, spend, borrow, and invest money directly influences national economic growth.

Financial literacy plays an important role in this process. It helps households make better decisions about savings, formal bankings, loans, and investments. When households manage their finances wisely, they support productive

investment and economic stability. However, high dependence on informal debt and low participation in financial assets can limit growth potential.

This study uses data from the NSS 77th Round – All India Debt and Investment Survey (2019), conducted by the National Sample Survey Office under the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, to examine how household financial structure relates to India's growth path. The research is conducted in three stages: first, establishing a 2019 baseline of household financial behavior; second, extending the analysis to the present context; and third, projecting trends up to 2030 to identify the financial and policy changes needed to support

India's journey toward a 5-trillion-dollar economy.

Literature Review:

1) Title: Understanding Consumer Financial Behavior: Spending, Saving, Investing and Debt

Source: Advances in Consumer Research Volume 43

This research highlights that consumer financial decisions (spending, saving, investing, and debt repayment) are influenced by psychological factors. Studies show that frequent traders exhibit overconfidence, debt repayment increases with better framing, time perception affects saving behavior, and age influences risk decisions.

Key Insight: Financial behavior is shaped more by behavioral biases and framing effects than by pure rationality.

2) Title: The Role of Big Data Analytics in Behavioral Finance: Understanding Dynamics of Consumer Spending and Saving – Kyle Whitaker

This study explains how big data analytics helps understand consumer spending and saving behavior. By using transaction data, social media, and machine learning, it identifies psychological biases and patterns in financial decisions.

Key Insight: The integration of big data with behavioral finance improves understanding of financial decision-making and supports more accurate, data-driven financial strategies.

Objectives of the Study:

How do financial literacy and spending habits shape India's GDP growth and its goal of becoming the world's 3rd largest economy?"

Sub-objectives:

1. Study how financial literacy affects household consumption, savings, and investment.
2. Explore the role of FinTech, generational shifts, and cultural factors in spending.

3. Analyze sustainability, health, education, and housing as key GDP drivers.
4. Assess risks (stress, debt traps, NPAs(Non-Performing Assets)) vs. opportunities (digital economy, MSMEs).
5. Connect findings with India's 2030 GDP vision.

Distribution of Household Financial Assets:

This section presents the basic statistical properties of household financial assets, including measures of central tendency and dispersion. The purpose is to understand how financial wealth is distributed across households and to identify the presence of inequality in the dataset.

Financial Assets: Bank Balances, Cash, Fixed Deposits, Shares and Gold.

Physical Assets such as Real Estate (lands & Buildings), Livestock and Farm Machinery are not considered.

Measure of Central Tendency	Value
Minimum	Rs. 0
Maximum	Rs. 52 Crore
Mean	Rs. 9,46,457
Median	Rs. 2,28,132
First Quartile	Rs. 69,000
Third Quartile	Rs. 7,98,230

Insights:

- Minimum(Rs.0): Some households have very small to no financial assets. There are families with nearly zero savings, no bank balance and no investments. This shows the lowest financial group of India.
- Maximum(Rs. 52 Crore): These are extremely rich households which are very few in numbers but acting as an outlier.
- Mean(Rs. 9,46,457): This shows mean financial assets of household which is much high because mean is deviated due to

extremely rich households with very high financial assets.

- Median(Rs. 2,28,132): This is the actual condition of Indian households. A typical family has around Rs. 2.3 lakh in their financial assets.
- First Quartile(Rs. 69,000) & Third Quartile(Rs. 7,98,230): 25% of households have less than Rs. 69,000 in total assets. Means that one-fourth of Indian households are living with very little financial safety. Even a small emergency can create serious problem for them. 75% of households have less than Rs. 7.98 lakh in their financial assets.
- This all shows that wealth is not evenly spread.

The Macro-Financial Baseline of Indian Households (Savings & Investment):

- Before studying how financial literacy affects India's GDP, we first need a clear picture of country's household finances. The baseline table shows the total level of household savings, financial assets and debt in India. It helps us understand how much money families save, how much money they borrow, and how financially secure they are overall.
- By knowing this starting point, we can better analyze spending behavior, regional differences, and the role of household finances in supporting India's economic growth.

Indicator	Estimated value
Total Estimated Households	12.08 Crore households
National Financial Assets	Rs. 8.45 Lakh Crore
National Household Debt	Rs. 5.17 Lakh Crore
Financial Health Ratio (Assets/ Debt)	1.63

- Estimated Households: 12.08 Crore Households. This represents the total number of households in India that make everyday spending, saving and borrowing decisions.
- National Financial Assets: Rs. 8.45 Lakh Crore. This includes money that households own such as Bank deposits, Fixed deposits, Mutual funds, Shares, Insurance, Savings, Pension Funds, Shares, Bonds, etc.
- National Household Debt: Rs. 5.17 Lakh Crore. This represents estimated total household debts such as Home Loans, Education Loans, Vehicle Loans, Personal Loans, Credit card dues, etc.
- Financial Health Ratio: 1.63. This shows the financial condition of Indian households calculated by taking ratio of Assets and Debt. It represents – “ For every Rs. 1 of debt, households have Rs. 1.63 of financial assets”.

Key Insights:

- Indian households hold more assets than debt, which financial stability and careful spending behavior.
- Better job security, insurance and public services can reduce financial fear and encourage households to spend more, take more financial decisions leads to rise of GDP.
- A large share of household saving is kept in low-return deposits. Redirecting these funds toward businesses, infrastructure, and financial markets can support economic growth.
- Heavy investment in land, housing, and gold limits liquidity. Greater use of financial instruments can improve money circulation in the economy.
- Household debt includes both useful loans and risky informal borrowing. Expanding

access to affordable institutional credit can turn borrowing into a tool for income growth.

- Small income improvements in rural areas can create large national economic gains due to their large population share.

Structure of Household Debt:

A) Source of Household Debt: Source of Household debt in India (NSS 77th Round)

Agency Type	Total Debt (Rs. Crores)	Percentage	Risk Rating
Institutional (Banks/ Govt)	Rs.20,30,961	39.3%	Low Risk
Non-Institutional (Informal)	Rs. 31,35,175	60.7%	High Risk

Household borrowing in India is largely dependent on non-institutional sources. Around 60.7% of total debt originates from informal lenders, while only 39.3% comes from banks or government institutions. This indicates limited use of regulated credit markets and suggests higher borrowing risk for many households.

Key Insights:

- Most households take loans from informal lenders like moneylenders, relatives, or friends.
- Loans from banks and formal institutions are fewer but safer.
- Taking too many informal loans can lead to high interest and repayment problems.
- Many households still do not have easy access to bank loans.
- Improving financial literacy and access to banking services can help people borrow more safely.

B) Purpose-wise distribution of Household Debt: To understand how households use borrowed money and whether debt is taken mainly for productive investment or daily consumption. This helps identify financial risk and long-term economic impact.

Purpose category	Total Amount (Rs. Crore)	Share (%)	Economic Impact
Consumption/ Social/ Medical	1,945,306	37.7%	Wealth Depletion
Productive (Business/ Farm)	45,928	0.9%	Low Capital Growth
Housing/ Construction	48,199	0.9%	Asset Building
Other/ Unspecified	3,126,704	60.5%	High Uncertainty

Key Insights:

- Most loans are used for consumption and social needs, not for income generation.
- Very little debt is used for business or farming, so borrowing does not help economic growth much.
- Housing loans are also very small, showing limited investment in assets.
- A large share of debt is in “Other” category, which shows poor financial planning and uncertainty.
- Overall, households borrow more for short-term needs than long-term wealth creation.

This shows that household debt in India is mainly used for survival needs rather than productive investment.

Financial Inclusion and Credit Gap:**A) Geographic & Sectoral Analysis of Household Credit Access:**

Sector	Bank Access Rate(%)	Informal Debt Share(%)	Primary Financial Risk
Rural	100%	53.2%	High dependence on moneylenders despite being banked.
Urban	100%	42.1%	Urban households still rely heavily on informal loans.

To compare rural and urban households in terms of access to formal banking and dependence on informal borrowing. This helps identify financial inclusion gaps and regional credit risks in India.

Insights:

- Even though both rural and urban families have bank accounts, many still borrow from moneylenders.
- Rural households depend more on informal loans than urban households.
- This shows that having a bank account does not mean people use formal banking services.
- Lack of financial knowledge and trust in banks increases informal borrowing.
- Money taken from informal lenders stays outside the banking system, slowing economic growth.

The results show a clear rural–urban financial literacy gap. Despite universal bank access in the sample, informal borrowing remains high, especially in rural areas. This indicates that financial inclusion in India is more about usage and awareness than account ownership.

B) Inferential Analysis of Rural–Urban Credit Source Dependence:

To test whether the source of household borrowing (institutional vs informal) is statistically associated with place of residence (rural vs urban).

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no relationship between the sector (Rural/ Urban) and the type of lender.

H₁: There is a relationship between the sector (Rural/ Urban) and the type of lender.

Contingency Table

Sector	Institutional	Non-Institutional	Total Households
Rural	35,698	74,495	110,193
Urban	26,351	42,427	68,778

A Chi-Square test of independence was conducted to examine the relationship between residence (rural vs urban) and source of debt.

The test was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 654.36$, $p < 0.001$, indicating that borrowing source is strongly associated with location.

- Rural households depend more on informal lenders compared to urban households.
- This suggests that financial inclusion is uneven across regions.
- Access to banks does not automatically translate into usage of formal credit.
- Structural barriers such as awareness, availability of services, and trust in institutions may explain this gap.

These findings highlight the need for stronger financial literacy programs, easier access to formal credit in rural areas, and monitoring of informal lending practices. Improving institutional credit usage can reduce interest burden and support productive investment.

Inequality Analysis:

A) Wealth Inequality Analysis Using the Gini Coefficient:

To measure the level of wealth inequality among households in the sample using the Gini Coefficient and examine its implications for financial participation and economic growth.

The Gini Coefficient is a widely used measure of inequality ranging from 0 (perfect equality) to 1 (perfect inequality). Higher values indicate greater concentration of wealth among fewer households.

Estimated Gini Coefficient = 0.716

A Gini value above 0.70 means that wealth is very unevenly distributed. A small number of households own most of the financial assets, while many households have very little wealth.

B) Lorenz Curve Analysis of Household Financial Wealth:

To visually examine how financial wealth is distributed among households, we plotted the Lorenz Curve. This graph compares the share of total wealth owned by different population groups and helps us understand the level of inequality in financial assets.

- The Lorenz curve lies far below the equality line, showing high wealth inequality.
- A large share of households owns only a small portion of total financial wealth.
- Wealth is concentrated among a small number of households.
- The rural curve shows slightly less inequality than the national average.
- These results support the high Gini coefficient found earlier.

The Lorenz curve is far from the equality line, which shows high wealth inequality. Most households own only a small share of total wealth, while a few hold most of it. The rural curve shows slightly less inequality than the national average, supporting the high Gini value calculated earlier.

Variable	Estimate	P-value	Significance
Intercept	-1.70e ⁻⁰¹	8.8e-07	Highly Significant
Assets	-3.003e ⁻⁰³	<2e-16	Highly Significant
Education	4.58e ⁻⁰³	0.148	Not Significant
Bank Access	-1.561e ⁻⁰⁴	0.321	Not Significant

Factors Influencing informal Debt Traps in Indian Households: The study uses logistic regression to predict the probability of a household falling into an informal Debt Trap.

Insights:

- Assets: Households with more assets are much less likely to fall into informal debt traps.
- Education: Education alone does not significantly reduce the risk of informal debt.
- Family Size: Family size does not have a meaningful effect on debt trap risk.

- Bank Access: Having a bank account alone is not enough to reduce debt trap risk.

Financial Persona Segmentation of Indian Households: The K-Means clustering used to group households with similar patterns of assets, debt, education, and bank access. This helps identify different financial personas instead of only rural-urban categories.

Cluster No.	Cluster Name	
1	Educated Leveragers	Households with moderate assets and high formal borrowing. They use credit for growth.
2	Vulnerable Majority	Households with low assets and high debt burden. They are financially risky and need support.
3	High Stake Entrepreneurs	Wealthier households with high borrowing for business or investment.

Financial Persona Segments (NSS 77th Round)

Conclusions:

- **Indian households are net savers:** Assets are higher than debt, showing cautious spending behavior.
- **Wealth is highly unequal:** Financial assets are concentrated among a small number of households.
- **Most households are financially vulnerable:** A large group has low assets and depends on debt for daily needs.
- **Informal borrowing is still common:** Many households rely on non-institutional credit, increasing financial risk.
- **Assets give protection from debt traps:** Households with higher assets are less likely to fall into risky borrowing.
- **Bank access supports wealth growth:** Households with better access to formal finance have higher assets.
- **Different financial personas exist:** Clustering shows distinct household types that need different policies.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study uses data from 2019, so it may not show recent changes in the economy after COVID-19.
- The survey is for one time period only, so we cannot track how household behaviour changes over time.
- The data is based on household responses, so some values may be inaccurate or under-reported.
- Financial literacy is not measured directly in the dataset; it is only guessed from spending and saving behaviour.
- Some informal savings and loans may not be fully captured in the survey.
- The link between household finance and GDP is based on analysis, not direct proof of cause and effect.

- Statistical models like clustering and regression depend on assumptions, which may affect results.

Future Scope of the Study:

- Future research can use updated survey data to study changes in household financial behaviour after 2019.
- A panel (long-term) dataset can help track how savings, debt, and investment patterns change over time.
- Direct measures of financial literacy can be included to better understand its real impact on economic growth.
- More advanced forecasting models can be used to improve GDP projections for 2030.
- The study can be expanded to compare India with other developing countries.
- Policy-based simulations can be added to test how financial inclusion programs may affect household wealth and GDP.
- Digital finance and fintech adoption can also be studied as new drivers of financial growth.

References:

1. Joseph Harvey, University of Colorado, USA Michal Strahilevitz, Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand - Understanding Consumer Financial Behavior: Spending, Saving, Investing and Debt.
2. Kyle Whitaker - The Role of Big Data Analytics in Behavioral Finance: Understanding Dynamics of Consumer Spending and Saving.
3. Ferdinando Giglio – Fintech
4. Rinshu Dwivedi¹ and Jalandhar Pradhan² - International Journal for Equity and Health Does equity in healthcare spending exist among Indian states? Explaining regional variations from national sample survey data.